

Title: Pandemonium Quintet play Drone & Drama Versions

1. PROGRAM NOTES

Pandemonium quintet play DIY electronic musical instruments (EMI). The group consists of five highly experienced music improvisers, visual artists and instrument makers dedicated to bringing audiences the finest in folktronic audio and cybernetic signals, vibrating together in heart-warming 12V ballads, oscillating between the sacred and the profane.

Our current performance system is a synthesis of bespoke video and previously existing musical circuits that have been modified to promote productive instability within a restricted set of timbral possibilities. The aesthetic of our performance is informed by noise and free improvised musics.

Fig. 1. pandemonium quintet NIME2023 app v1_1.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Pandemonium quintet was set up to explore multiple versions of DIY EMI through improvisation.

We are particularly interested in exploiting irregularities in the qualities of circuit components (e.g. imprecise tolerances/values), and how this allows for the development of stylistic differences across multiple instrument-performer configurations. We are also interested in how skill, style and performance techniques are developed in different ways on similar devices over extended periods of time, and how our existing musical practices are reconfigured through such collaborative exchanges.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

For this musical performance each performer will use versions of Drone & Drama EMI featuring function generators and wide band noise. The instruments are ‘bent by design’ [1] and use ‘withered technologies’[2] at their core.

We require a PA, an audio mixer with at least 5 inputs, one large table and access to mains power. Discrete stage monitors would be desirable, depending on performance space. A video projector and screen is also required.

Media Link

- Video: <https://vimeo.com/797750343>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the NIME community

ETHICAL STANDARDS

Please note, that if any elements of the submitted work involve research with people or animals, authors should include a section “Compliance with Ethical Standards” before the References, including (if relevant): information regarding sources of funding, potential conflicts of interest (financial or non-financial), informed consent if the research involved human participants, statement on welfare of animals if the research involved animals.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Hordijk, “The Blippoo Box: A Chaotic Electronic Music Instrument, Bent by Design,” *Leonardo Music J.*, vol. 19, pp. 35–43, 2009.
- [2] M. Ott, “Lateral Thinking With Withered Technology,” *Matthias Ott – User Experience Designer*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://matthiasott.com/notes/lateral-thinking-with-withered-technology>. [Accessed: 25-Oct-2022].